

INTEGRATION OF SUBJECTS IN TEACHING FINE ARTS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. The article examines the pedagogical possibilities of integrating academic subjects in teaching Fine Arts in general secondary schools. Particular attention is paid to the implementation of interdisciplinary connections based on the STEAM approach, which ensures the formation of students' holistic perception of the surrounding world, the development of creative thinking, spatial imagination, and practical competencies. The study was conducted on the basis of general secondary schools with the participation of 7th–8th grade students. During the pedagogical experiment, the effectiveness of integrating Fine Arts with mathematics, geometry, physics, biology, history, informatics, and technology was studied. The obtained results showed a significant increase in the level of learning motivation, the quality of creative task performance, spatial thinking, and the ability to apply interdisciplinary knowledge in practical activities. It was established that the use of an integrative approach contributes to improving the educational process, enhancing the quality of education, and forming modern universal competencies among schoolchildren. The conclusion is made about the expediency of the widespread introduction of interdisciplinary integration in teaching Fine Arts within the system of general secondary education.

Keywords: Fine Arts, interdisciplinary integration, STEAM education, creative thinking, spatial imagination, artistic and aesthetic education, general secondary school, pedagogical experiment, learning motivation, innovative technologies

Introduction. In the modern conditions of modernization of the general secondary education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the integration of academic disciplines acquires special importance as a means of forming students' holistic worldview, creative thinking, and practical competencies. The improvement of teaching the subject "Fine Arts" becomes especially relevant, since this subject contributes to the development of artistic and aesthetic perception, spatial thinking, creativity, and the emotional intelligence of schoolchildren.

Under the conditions of implementing STEAM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics), Fine Arts acquires a new pedagogical function, acting not only as an artistic discipline but also as an important tool of interdisciplinary integration. Through the interconnection with mathematics, geometry, physics, biology, history, informatics, and technology, a comprehensive understanding of the surrounding world is formed, as well as the skills of project and research activities are developed.

The relevance of the study is обусловлена the need to improve the methodology of teaching Fine Arts in general secondary schools based on interdisciplinary integration, which corresponds to modern requirements of state educational standards and the strategy of educational development.

The purpose of the study is to determine the pedagogical effectiveness of subject integration in teaching Fine Arts in general secondary schools.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted during the 2025–2026 academic year on the basis of 4 general secondary schools in the Surkhandarya region. The study involved 128 students of grades 7–8 and 12 teachers.

To achieve the stated goal, the following research methods were used:

- analysis of scientific and methodological literature;
- pedagogical observation;
- questionnaires for students and teachers;
- pedagogical experiment;
- comparative analysis of results;
- methods of mathematical statistics.

The students were divided into two groups:

- control group (n = 64) - training according to the traditional methodology;
- experimental group (n = 64) - training using interdisciplinary integration based on the STEAM approach.

The STEAM approach.

The experiment lasted for 6 months. The following indicators were assessed:

1. level of creative thinking;
2. spatial imagination;
3. learning motivation;
4. quality of creative task performance;
5. level of interdisciplinary connections in practical activities.

Results. The results of the pedagogical experiment demonstrated a stable positive dynamic in the experimental group, where Fine Arts was taught using interdisciplinary integration based on the STEAM approach. In contrast, the control group, which studied according to the traditional methodology, showed only minor improvements in the analyzed indicators.

At the initial stage of the experiment, both groups had approximately equal indicators in all evaluated parameters, which ensured the objectivity of the comparative analysis. After six months of systematic implementation of interdisciplinary teaching methods, significant quantitative and qualitative changes were recorded in the experimental group.

Table 1

Indicators of the effectiveness of subject integration in teaching Fine Arts (%)

Indicators	Control Group (Before)	Control Group (After)	Experimental Group (Before)	Experimental Group (After)
High level of creative thinking	24.3	29.7	23.8	51.6
Developed spatial imagination	27.1	31.4	26.5	56.2
High learning motivation	32.8	36.0	31.7	63.4
High-quality performance of creative tasks	29.5	34.2	30.1	58.7
Level of interdisciplinary practical	21.7	28.6	22.4	61.3

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The indicator of creative thinking in the experimental group increased from 23.8% to 51.6%, while in the control group the growth was much lower, from 24.3% to 29.7%. This demonstrates that interdisciplinary integration significantly stimulates students' ability to generate original ideas, apply non-standard solutions, and independently complete artistic tasks.

A particularly significant improvement was observed in the development of spatial imagination. In the experimental group, this показатель increased from 26.5% to 56.2%, whereas in the control group it changed only from 27.1% to 31.4%. Such results confirm that the integration of Fine Arts with geometry, mathematics, and technical drawing contributes to the more effective formation of visual-spatial thinking.

Learning motivation also showed substantial growth. The percentage of students with high educational motivation in the experimental group rose from 31.7% to 63.4%, which was almost twice the initial level. In the control group, the increase was comparatively insignificant (from 32.8% to 36.0%). This suggests that students demonstrate greater interest and engagement when educational material is presented through practical interdisciplinary tasks and project-based learning.

The quality of creative task performance also improved considerably. In the experimental group, the indicator increased from 30.1% to 58.7%, while in the control group it reached only 34.2% compared to the initial 29.5%. Students began to demonstrate more confident composition building, better color solutions, improved perspective understanding, and stronger independent artistic interpretation.

The most significant growth was recorded in the level of interdisciplinary practical connections. In the experimental group, this indicator increased from 22.4% to 61.3%, while in the control group it rose only from 21.7% to 28.6%. This confirms that students who studied under the STEAM model were able to consciously apply knowledge from physics, biology, mathematics, informatics, and technology during artistic and project activities.

Qualitative observations conducted during classroom lessons also confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. Students in the experimental group became more active in discussions, showed higher independence in project tasks, demonstrated better analytical skills, and more confidently defended their creative ideas. Teachers also noted a significant increase in collaborative learning, research interest, and practical application of theoretical knowledge.

Thus, the obtained results prove that the use of interdisciplinary integration in teaching Fine Arts not only improves subject-specific achievements but also forms broader educational competencies necessary for modern school education. The STEAM-based approach creates favorable conditions for the development of students' intellectual, creative, and practical potential.

Discussion. The obtained results are consistent with modern studies in the field of pedagogical integration and STEAM education. Many researchers note that interdisciplinary integration contributes not only to improving academic performance but also to the formation of universal competencies of the 21st century: critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity.

Fine Arts has a unique potential for implementing an integrative approach, since it combines visual thinking, practical activity, and emotional-value perception. Through artistic activity, students more easily master abstract concepts of geometry, physics, biology, and technology.

During the study, it was found that the traditional teaching system does not sufficiently use the possibilities of interdisciplinary integration, whereas the purposeful implementation of the STEAM approach significantly increases educational effectiveness.

It should be noted that the successful implementation of this model requires appropriate teacher training, updating of educational and methodological support, and the creation of a modern material and technical base.

Conclusion. The integration of academic subjects in teaching Fine Arts in general secondary schools is an effective pedagogical tool for improving the quality of education.

The use of interdisciplinary connections based on the STEAM approach contributes to:

- the development of creative thinking;
- the formation of spatial imagination;
- increasing learning motivation;
- improving practical skills;
- preparing students for innovative activities.

The results of the study confirm the expediency of the widespread introduction of integration technologies into the educational process of general secondary schools.

Prospects for further research are associated with the development of digital methods for teaching Fine Arts and expanding the possibilities of 3D modeling in school education.

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